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Microscopic Authentication of Pakistani Commercial Herbal Plants of Family Lamiaceae

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Abstract

Herbal medications become extremely crucial for global healthcare. Herbal plants are sold and utilized all over the world for their supposed or predicted health advantages, but their growing popularity culminated in a rise of accidental contamination or purposeful adulteration. The medicinally important, *Ocimum basilicum* member of the family Lamiaceae can be investigated using microscopic and pharmacognostic parameters. Microscopic characterization can be done by section cutting and observing under a light microscope (LM), but most magnified structures describing their anatomical features and morphology can be viewed using SEM (scanning electron microscope). While, pharmacognostic characterization is done by fluorescent analysis, solubility, and physiochemical analysis. Today's critical issue faced by the herbal market is uncertainty and conflict produced by the same synonyms used for more than one or two drugs. In herbal marketplaces, distinct species are sometimes marketed under the same common or local name, resulting in adulteration. Hence, it is concluded that as each plant has its own peculiar internal structures and chemical compounds. So, this article helps to compare the anatomical and powder structures with the already known structures in order to minimize the risk of adulteration.

Keywords: Authentication; *Ocimum basilicum*; Pharmacognostic analysis; Adulteration; Medically Important; Herbal Plants

1. Introduction:

The Lamiaceae or Labiatae (the mint or deadnettle family) area family of flowering plants. The 40 to 50 species of the genus *Lamium* are known as dead nettles; they are low-weedy plants that are sometimes cultivated. This family mainly includes chameophytes, herbs, and small shrubs with a cosmopolitan distribution rich in useful species worldwide (Heywood, 1978). The plants of Lamiaceae family are frequently aromatic in all parts and include many widely used culinary herbs, such as basil, mint, rosemary, sage, savory, marjoram, oregano, hyssop, thyme, lavender, and perilla. Some are shrubs; trees, such as teak; or, rarely, vines. This family has 250generas and 7850 species. Family Lamiaceae also

showed its extreme importance in the field of Pharmacognosy as it showed the variety of chemicals. Natural α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitors from food-grade plant sources are founded in this family, and thus offering an attractive strategy to control postprandial hyperglycemia. It can be used as an effective therapy for postprandial hyperglycemia with minimal side effects (Kown *et al.*, 2006).

Use of herbal plants is from the ancient times and this application can be seen in all earliest cultures and entirely on the continents. As a result, despite developments in pharmacology, the medicinal usage of plants still prevalent in several nations, particularly in underdeveloped nations (Chaachouay *et al.*, 2022). Herbal plants are sold as a whole, in fragments, as an extract, powder, or as a blend in herbal markets.

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Variable topographical locations, differences in variations, and nomenclatural ambiguity are the primary causes of adulteration in medicinal plants, laying the groundwork for quality control standards. At the moment, the main difficulty in the herbal sector is the lack of standardization of medicinal plants, since the untrustworthy behaviors of their dealers undermine local people's trust (Ahmed *et al.*, 2019).

Ocimum bascillum is an annual species, an herb grown as a perennial with a vegetative apparatus composed of a well-ramified fibrous root, a strongly ramified. Stem. Leaves are pointy ovate-lanceolate opposite leaves with attenuate serrate edges. Blade narrowly ovate-lanceolate almost elliptic, with entire

1.1. Objectives:

- To ensure quality assurance and prevent adulteration.
- Establishment of a comprehensive reference database of microscopic characteristics, supporting the herbal industry.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Collection of Plant Samples and Drying:

Plants material was collected from Akbari market Lahore, washed with simple tap water then identified by Sultan Ahmed herbarium in GCU, Lahore, and voucher nos. were taken and preserved in FAA (formalin 5ml, acetic acid 5ml and alcohol 50ml and final volume is raised up to 100 ml) in a closed container for section cutting and staining procedure. Few plant materials were dried under shade for 30 to 35 days until all the moisture in the sample was completely dried.

2.2. Preparation of Reagents:

For section cutting and staining the 30%, 50%, 70%, 80%, 90% and 100% alcohol solutions were prepared. 0.05% of fast green was prepared by dissolving 0.05% of this reagent in 100ml of 90% alcohol. 1% safranin solution was prepared by dissolving 1ml safranin in 100ml of 90% ethanol. 10% of the solution was then taken and final volume was raised up to 100ml by distilled water. For Powder study a solution of Chloralhydrate, NaOH, HCL, H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ was used and.

2.3. Macroscopic Evolution:

The macroscopic structures of *Ocimum bascillum* like leaves, stem and roots were noted. The leaves anatomy tells about the type of stomata present.

margins sparsely shallow-toothed, both sides short-haired. Flowers are showy and have fragrance. The flowers are showy and large in size. It is famous in Asia and all tropical areas in regards of its culinary, traditional, medicinal, and uses in pharmacy. It is a rich source of vitamins A, K, C, Mg, Fe, I and Ca. *Ocimum bascillum* was funded to have hepatoprotective activity this was also studied by (Meera *et al.*, 2009). And the ethanolic extract of *Ocimum bascillum* showed antiviral activities. These phenolic compounds were shown to have activity against HSV-1, HSV-2, ADV-3, ADV-8, ADV-11, CVB1, and EV71 viruses (Chiang *et al.*, 2005).

Stem anatomy shows the primary growth while root anatomy describes about the secondary growth.

2.4. Microscopic Evolution:

The internal structures like tracheids, vessels, pollen, scalariform in the leaves and stem of *Ocimum bascillum* shown by fluorescent analysis and physiochemical analysis method.

2.5. Powdery Microscopy:

Dry leaves, and stem of each sample were macerated separately in pestle and mortar with few drops of chloralhydrate solution with help of dropper until the mixture became homogenous solution type. Then took this solution with the help of dropper on the glass slide and covered it with cover slips then observed it under light microscopy by using different objective lenses. Different microscopic structures like xylem, parenchymatous tissues, helical and pitted vessels, epidermal cells, pollen were seen clearly in labomed microscope under the objective lens of 40x.

2.6. Fluorescent Analysis:

The fluorescent analysis of the whole plant is done by treating 1g of dried powdered treated with different chemicals reagents like 1N NaOH, 1N HCl, 50% H₂SO₄, 50% HNO₃, as well as with distilled water. And then this mixture visualized under an ordinary light, the short UV light of (254nm), and long UV light of (366nm) under UV chamber, obtained different colors. Fluorescence analysis is a key method for screening substances that display distinct colour when exposed to UV light. Some chemicals are not luminous by itself, but when exposed to solutions, they are transformed into fluorescent compounds. The shift in colour was seen during this investigation (Ansari, 2007).

2.6. Physicochemical Analysis:

Physicochemical parameters such as the % of loss on drying (LOD), total ash, acid insoluble ash value, water soluble ash value and sulphate ash values were determined according to Indian Pharmacopoeia (Kumar *et al.*, 2013).

3. Results:

3.1. Anatomical Results:

The following anatomical structures had seen under SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope).

Figure 1: Interactive effect of extracting solvent and different parts of plants on extract yield

The following microscopic structures were seen under 40x.

Figure 2: Leaves Powder of *Ocimum basilicum* shows A. Diacytic type of stomata surrounding subsidiary cells in its leaves B. Hexacolpate pollen grain in leaves powder C. Stomata embedded in epidermis D. Helical Vessels

Figure 3: Stem powder of *Ocimum Bascillum* A. Scalariform with perforations B. Pitted vessel C. Helical vessels D. Parenchymatous tissues

Table 1: Fluorescent behaviour of powder of *Ocimum bascillum*.under visible and UV light

S. No.	Solvent used	Day light	254nm (UV light)	360nm (UV light)
1	Powder + 1N NaOH (Aqueous)	Pale yellow	Light brown	Green
2	Powder + 1N HCl	Dark brown	Reddish brown	White
3	Powder + 50% H ₂ SO ₄	brown	Light brown	Yellow
4	Powder + 50% HNO ₃	orange	white	Dark green
5	1% KOH	Yellowish brown	Chocolate brown	Light yellow
6	Powder as such	Light yellow	yellow	Green

Table 2: Physio-chemical analysis of powdered plant samples

S. No.	Plant Name	Loss of weight on drying	Total ash value	Water insoluble ash	Acid insoluble ash	Sulphated ash
1	<i>Ocimum bascillum</i>	41.28%w/w	31.51%w/w	4.32%w/w	1.21%w/w	2.15%w/w

4. Discussion:

The characteristics feature of Lamiaceae having quadrangular stem and the presence of collenchyma and sclerenchyma's surrounds the vascular tissues. Collenchymas are present in stem corners while no sclerenchyma was investigatednor in contrast to those described by Metcalfe & Chalk, (1983). Herbalplants are not only economically important but also important in maintaining the life system on Earth. The

plants with the potential capacity for the treatment of various diseases and are used by people from the past are called medicinal plants by Kumar & Kanwar, (2020).

In developing countries, the acceptance of herbal plants is hindered by many problems, one of which is a lack of quality control and documentation. Due to this drawback, standardization of herbal content to be used as the treatment of different diseases is important. It is to be accomplished by the quantity and quality

pharmacognostic research including morphological, biochemical characterization and anatomical analysis. The authentication and identification of plant material is done by standardization. A significant prerequisite in the reproducible value of medicinal plants which contribute to their efficacy and protection is assured by correct identification and quality insurance of initial constituents (Shweta *et al.*, 2012).

Ocimum bascillum has a morphology showing large leaves. On touching the leaf surface has smooth appearance. The stem of it was herbaceous in nature and easy to cut off. On maturation the lower part of the stem shows woody appearance and become hard. This is due to the secondary growth also described by Maria *et al.* (2008).

In the epidermis of *Ocimum bascillum* L. studied under LM at 40x and SEM stomata were diacytic bearing multicellular trichomes on it also reported by Metcalf & Chalk (1965). Similarly, when seen under SEM and LM It showed epidermis with more stomatas on upper surface and less on lower surface. Our results were in consistent with Kundalic *et al.* (2009).

While in stem of *Ocimum bascillum* when observed under the SEM showed the similarity in quadrangular shape. below epidermis collenchyma cells with angular thickening were distinctively present, a distinguishing character of family Lamiaceae as already reported by Metcalf & Chalk (1965); Maria *et al.* (2008) bearing collateral vascular bundles was the layer of collenchyma cells with thick wall. Below collenchyma cells is the cortical region made up of parenchymatous cells. Stem being quadrangular in shape has four Costas. Each bearing set of vascular bundles.

Fluorescent analysis of all the plants powders were carried out based on method the of Semwal *et al.* (2013). 1N NaOH, 50% HNO_3 , H_2SO_4 and 1% KOH reagents were used in the fluorescent analysis. Different chemicals were used in the fluorescent analysis of all the plant samples that showed different coloration under visible light and UV light that was listed in Table 1.

In Table 2, the ash content of plant material has been listed. The amount of impurities and any adulteration is determined by fluorescent analysis. After combustion, the ash content of all plants part remained varies considerably depending upon the plant part, age, treatment etc. The ash constituents of a sample vary from organ to organ and with time. Acid soluble value can determine the organ constituents by Momin & Kadam, (2011).

Ocimum bascillum has two types of trichomes one as simple multicellular and other as branched, forming a star shape, originating from a single point. As investigated under powder microscopy (Werker *et al.*, 1993).

Root of *Ocimum bascillum* is woody and has shown

secondary growth thus occupying a large mass of xylem cells as Protoxylem and metaxylem. The xylem cells were completely surrounded by the sclerenchyma cells. Phloem is present below the sclerenchyma cells (Kandemir, 2003).

Ocimum bascillum's powder extract showed, Hexacolpate pollen grain by Gird *et al.* (2015), and other structures like Diacytic stomata, hook trichome, helical vessels, scalariform with perforations, and parenchymatous tissues. Similar results were reported by Sarma & Babu, (2011) in *Ocimum americanum* specie.

The presence of adulterants in drugs and improper drug are handling of drugs are determined by the physicochemical parameter. Important quantitative standards are the ash values (Rajesh *et al.*, 2010) and these are the criterion that is used to analyze the purity and identity of drugs (Patnia *et al.*, 2012). The care taken in the preservation of drugs, purity of drugs and preparation of drugs are also reflected by the total ash values of crud drugs (Purohit *et al.*, 2005).

5. Conclusion:

The easiest and the cheapest way for the authentication of herbal plants is microscopy that cope with the mixture and impurities present in it. Since the consumption rate of herbal medication is increasing day by day so it is essential to minimize the rate of standardization. Study conducted under scanning electron microscope has helped to make this all investigation helpful. Powder microscopy has helped to reveal various cells that cannot be easily identified under simple microscope. The epidermis of leaves of *Ocimum bascillum* shows Diacytic type of stomata, midrib showing vascular bundles, mesophyll cells, parenchymatous tissues and roots shows xylem cavity and tracheids under SEM. While their powder study reveals Hexacolpate pollen grain in their leaves, spiral vessels, helical vessel, tracheids, scalariform with perforations etc. The fluorescent analysis shows different colors under different parameters and under UV light of 254nm and 360nm. Ash value parameters tells about the percentage impurities present in plant sample. Impurities can also be determined by comparing the plant sample with the already sample of that plant present.

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